

Radiological Methods Preferred for the Assessment of Tubal Infertility: A Clinical Data-Based Approach¹

Lana Ezieshvili

Tbilisi State Medical University Department of Clinical Radiology

Otar urushadze

Tbilisi State Medical University Department of Clinical Radiology

urushadze@tsmu.edu

Levan Ratiani

Tbilisi State Medical University department of Critical Medicine

ratiani @ tsmu.edu

Nicolas Kintraia

Tbilisi State Medical University Departamnet of Obstetric and Gynecology

n.kintraia@ tsmu.edu.

Abstract

Infertility is an important problem of reproductive health nowadays; more than a million couples attend reproductive health clinics worldwide yearly. Fertility problems deeply affect women's mental, emotional, and sexual lives. There are several common causes of infertility, including ovulatory dysfunction, a male factor of infertility, and tubal disease.

Based on TSMU, The First University Clinic, the Department of Clinical Radiology, between 2021 and 2024, we studied 40 cases of female infertility. The age of patients varied between 25 and 36 years. In all studied cases, the reason to address the hospital was primary infertility, with an already excluded male factor. For the assessment of tubes in all 40 cases, we have used sonoHSG and HSG with 2–3-day intervals in the first phase of the menstrual cycle.

Among 40 patients initially, we did an observational transvaginal ultrasound to assess the anatomy of reproductive organs, followed by sonoHSG using hyper and hypoechogenic contrast media. In 20 cases we have defined different types of tubal occlusion: 4 cases of bilateral and 16 cases of unilateral. In all 20 cases, the results of HSG performed after sonoHSG were similar.

The results of our study revealed that the assessment of tubal patency by sonoHSG and HSG shows similar results. As the location of the tubal occlusion does not have

¹Address Author Correspondence to Lana Ezieshvili at lezieshvili@gmail.com

Accepted: 24 December 2024 / Published online: 28 December 2024

© The Author(s), 2024. Paper ID, 400125

any impact on future management, sonoHSG can be used as the initial method of tubal assessment, with minimal risks of side effects and absence of radioactive influence on reproductive organs.

Keywords

Female Infertility, SonoHSG, HSG, Tubal Occlusion, Tubal Patency Assessment.

Introduction

Up to 30 percent of couples trying to conceive worldwide are thought to have unexplained infertility. Which is a diagnosis of exclusion, and requires a highly qualified medical staff and appropriate diagnostic testing. J.A. Collins et. al. Infertility is an important problem of reproductive health nowadays; more than a million couples attend reproductive health clinics worldwide yearly. Fertility problems deeply affect women's mental, emotional, and sexual lives. Infertility is a socioeconomic and healthcare system problem; the absence of standardized diagnostic and management protocols has a great impact on outcomes [1,2,3,4,5].

The first most frequent cause of infertility is an ovulatory dysfunction; the second most common reason is a male factor of infertility; and the third one is a tubal factor. Almost 15% of infertility has unexplained reasons. Lifestyle and environmental factors are known to have a great impact on reproduction; commonly, smoking and obesity can adversely affect the reproductive system of a woman. American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists Committee opinion No. 589 Education, enhanced awareness, and age of the fertile population have effects on a decision to conceive. Advanced female age is associated with a decreased rate of fertility and an increased rate of abnormal pregnancy outcomes [6,7,8,9].

Assessment of tubal patency is an important and initial step in the clinical judgment of infertile patients; almost a third of female infertility is associated with tubal damage. The result of primary examinations plays a key role in a proper diagnosis and plan of management.

Laparoscopic chromopertubation and X-ray hysterosalpingography (HSG) until now are the main methods for the assessment of tubal patency. However, both methods have very well-known limitations and disadvantages: laparoscopy is an invasive procedure requiring hospitalization and general anesthesia and is associated with surgical risks. HSG is an outpatient procedure with an increased risk of allergic reactions to contrast media, exposure to radiation, and pain. One of the important disadvantages of hysterosalpingography is that visualization of the ovaries and pelvic lesions is impossible.

Recently, sonoHSG has been introduced as an alternative method for the assessment of fallopian tubes. The method does not require hospitalization; the procedure is short-lasting, easily repeatable, safe, inexpensive, and well-tolerated by the majority of patients. Athanasios Chalazonitis et al.: Hysterosalpingography is a radiographic imaging of internal reproductive organs: cervical canal, uterine cavity, fallopian tubes, and peritoneal cavity, by the injection of contrast media with fluoroscopic and visualization. It is performed with the minimum radiation [10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17].

Different forms of contrast media are used to improve medical imaging. One of the most disturbing side effects of the contrast media is an allergy that limits the use of the method. ACR Manual on Contrast Media: Treatment of contrast media reactions needs a special kit of medicines, qualified staff, and equipment that needs preparation before the procedure and must include an entire spectrum of potential adverse events [18].

SonoHSG allows visualizing the endometrium and ovaries with high-quality resolution and confirms the fact of tubal patency when contrast media pour into the abdominal cavity. Fallopian tubes play the most important role in the process of fertilization.

Assessment of fallopian tubes is one of the most important diagnostic opportunities to estimate the female reproductive system; it also shortens the time of identifying the reason and plan of consequent management. Dr. Tejaswi Chalumuri et al. Sonohysterosalpingography is a comparatively new method to assess tubal patency by using a transvaginal scan. It has several advantages over hysterosalpingography (HSG), mainly the absence of radiation and pain [19,20].

Material and method

In the First University Clinic Department of Clinical Radiology between 2021 and 2024, we studied 40 cases of reproductive-aged (25-36 years old) women. In all cases, the reason to address the hospital was infertility with an already excluded male factor. In all cases, we have received signed informed consent from patients, which has been elaborated and confirmed by the Ethics Board of our clinic. In all 40 cases, we have used sonoHSG and HSG for the assessment of tubes. In 34 cases, we have diagnosed secondary infertility with a history of STD (Figure 1). In 12 cases, medical history was aggravated by artificial abortion. Dilatation and curettage of the uterine cavity were used in 3 cases, and 1 case was complicated by post-abortion endometritis

Figure 1

Study inclusion criteria:

1. Reproductive age
2. The first case of addressing the hospital

3. Absence of male factor of infertility
4. Absence of pregnancy proved by blood HSG test
5. Signed informed consent

In all 40 patients, we have used diagnostic methods—HSG and sonoHSG. The combination of these two methods aimed to assess their diagnostic value.

The assessment of patients has been done at 2–3-day intervals, in the first phase of the menstrual cycle, with standard vaginal swab bacterioscopy and overview ultrasound for primary assessment of reproductive organs. We preferred to use transvaginal ultrasound to enhance visualization of reproductive organs.

During sonoHSG, the cervix was visualized by Cusco speculum and cleaned with an antiseptic solution without using a toothed tenaculum for cervical immobilization, thus excluding the risk of tubal spasm as a reflective reaction to the pain and the possibility of false positive results. Before insertion into a uterine cavity, the catheter was washed with saline solution to decrease the chances of echogenic mistakes. The balloon catheter was positioned on the level of the internal cervical os and followed by inflation with saline solution to keep it immobile and obstruct the cervical canal from pouring the contrast media. We have used hyper- and hypoechogenic contrasts to enhance visualization.

During the infusion of the contrast by the ultrasound, we scanned the uterus in a longitudinal view to confirm the pouring of the contrast into the abdominal cavity. In the case of patent tubes, contrast media pours freely, occurring in a Douglas pouch and giving the possibility to visualize ovaries apparently. In major cases, tubal patency assessed by HSG was proved by contrast media shifting along the tubes and homolateral parts of the abdominal cavity. During HSG, we used 10 ml of contrast media, followed by four consequent X-ray pictures. The first picture shows the early filling phase of the uterus, the second total filling phase of the uterus, the third filling of tubes, and the fourth pouring of the contrast into an abdominal cavity. In all cases, visualization of the tubes and interpretation of the results were adequate. During HSG, the patient receives radiation equal to 0.9-1.0 millisievert effective dose, equal to radiation received naturally during 4 months. Instead of such a low dose, radiation of reproductive organs and the risk of allergy reactions to contrast media still challenge medical staff and patients.

Results of the study

Our study aimed to assess tubal patency—total or partial, unilateral or bilateral occlusion.

In all 40 patients initially, we did the observational transvaginal ultrasound to assess the anatomy of reproductive organs, followed by sonohtsterosalpingography to define tubal patency using hyper and hypoechogenic contrast media. In 20 cases, we have defined different types of tubal occlusion: Bilateral occlusion was diagnosed in 4 cases when contrast media was not poured into Douglas's pouch (Figure 2). All four ladies had a history of STD; the rest of the 16 cases of sonoHSG revealed unilateral tubal occlusion (Figure 3), and we have planned HSG after 2-3 days. In 5 cases it was the left side tubal occlusion, and in 11 cases, the right side tubal block.

Figure 2 SonoHSG, Bilateral tubal block. Absence of waterfall.

Figure 3 SonoHSG ransvaginul ultrasound shows uterine cavity and the Douglas pouch filled with the fluid indicating the patency of the tube.

In all 20 cases the results of HSG and sonoHSG was similar (Figure 4).

Figure 4 Results of sonoHSG and HSG

Discussion

Our study has revealed that, for the assessment of the tubal patency, the accuracy of the results using sonoHSG and HSG is similar.

During the development of radiology, female reproductive organs were assessed only by X-rays; because of gonad radiation, the role of this method was very limited. Since the implementation of ultrasonography, it has become one of the most important methods for the assessment of female reproductive organs. Ultrasonography has no contraindications or side effects and possible to use in any phase of the menstrual cycle. For the assessment of tubal patency, the diagnostic value of ultrasound increases with a combination of hyper- and hypoechogenic contrast media without any radioactive influence on the gonads of women of reproductive age. Although the dose of radiation used during HSG is very low, it's still challenging for patients and medical staff. Contrast media used during HSG may induce nausea, vomiting, rash, alertness, etc. Comparison of diagnostic accuracy of sonoHSG and HSG to assess tubal patency gives us the possibility to enhance the importance of ultrasound in reproductive health and decrease possible side effects and the radioactive influence of x-rays on gonads. Our study has shown that the diagnostic accuracy of tubal patency by sonoHSG and HSG is similar for assessing tubal patency, but the determination of the place of occlusion is possible only by using HSG. As the location of tubal occlusion does not have any impact on future management, sonoHSG is considered to be an informative method for the assessment of tubal patency.

Study limitation

The limitation of the present study is that it was conducted in one hospital with a small number of patients in both study groups and a short duration between 2021 and 2024. This necessitates conducting additional clinical studies to verify the validity of the results.

Conclusion

The results of our study have revealed that the assessment of tubal patency is equally accurate by sonoHSG and HSG. As the location of the tubal occlusion does not have any impact on future management, sonoHSG can be used as the initial method of tubal assessment, with minimal risks of side effects and absence of radioactive influence on reproductive organs. Hyper-and anechogenic contrast media increase the informative value of the method.

Reference

1. [J.A. Collins, P.G. Crosignani](#). Unexplained infertility: a review of diagnosis, prognosis, treatment efficacy and management. *International Journal of Gynecology and Obstetrics*. [Volume39, Issue4](#), Pages 267-275. [doi.org/10.1016/0020-7292\(92\)90257-J](https://doi.org/10.1016/0020-7292(92)90257-J)
2. [Anupa Nandi MRCOG](#). Unexplained subfertility: diagnosis and management. *TOG Obstetrics Gynecology* [Volume18, Issue2](#). Pages 107-115. April 2016. doi.org/10.1111/tog.12253
3. M. Brandes, C.J.C.M. Hamilton, J.O.M. van der Steen et.al. Unexplained infertility: overall ongoing pregnancy rate and mode of conception. *Human Reproduction*, Volume 26, Issue 2, Pages 360–368. February 2011. doi.org/10.1093/humrep/deq349.

4. Brandes M 1, Hamilton CJ , van der Steen JO et.al. Unexplained infertility: overall ongoing pregnancy rate and mode of conception. *Human Reproduction* (Oxford, England), 16 Dec 2010, 26(2):360-368 <https://doi.org/10.1093/humrep/deq349>.
5. [A. Garolla](#), [D. Pizzol](#), [C. Foresta](#) et.al. Practical Clinical and Diagnostic Pathway for the Investigation of the Infertile Couple. *Front Endocrinol* (Lausanne) 2021 Jan 19;11:591837. doi: 10.3389/fendo.2020.591837. eCollection 2020.
6. American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists Committee on Gynecologic Practice and Practice Committee. Female age-related fertility decline: committee opinion No. 589. *Fertil Steril*. 2014;101(3):633–634. doi: 10.1016/j.fertnstert.2013.12.032
7. [Juan Balasch](#)¹, [Eduard Gratacós](#). Delayed childbearing: effects on fertility and the outcome of pregnancy. *Curr Opin Obstet Gynecol*. 24(3):187-93. 2012 Jun; doi: [J.A. Collins](#), [P.G. Crosignani](#). Unexplained infertility: a review of diagnosis, prognosis, treatment efficacy and management. *International Journal of Gynecology and Obstetrics*. [Volume39, Issue4](#), Pages 267-275. doi.org/10.1016/0020-7292(92)90257-J
8. [Anupa Nandi MRCOG](#). Unexplained subfertility: diagnosis and management. *TOG Obstetrics Gynecology* [Volume18, Issue2](#). Pages 107-115. April 2016. doi.org/10.1111/tog.12253
9. M. Brandes, C.J.C.M. Hamilton, J.O.M. van der Steen et.al. Unexplained infertility: overall ongoing pregnancy rate and mode of conception. *Human Reproduction*, Volume 26, Issue 2, Pages 360–368. February 2011. doi.org/10.1093/humrep/deq349.
10. Brandes M 1, Hamilton CJ , van der Steen JO et.al. Unexplained infertility: overall ongoing pregnancy rate and mode of conception. *Human Reproduction* (Oxford, England), 16 Dec 2010, 26(2):360-368 <https://doi.org/10.1093/humrep/deq349>.
11. [A. Garolla](#), [D. Pizzol](#), [C. Foresta](#) et.al. Practical Clinical and Diagnostic Pathway for the Investigation of the Infertile Couple. *Front Endocrinol* (Lausanne) 2021 Jan 19;11:591837. doi: 10.3389/fendo.2020.591837. eCollection 2020.
12. American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists Committee on Gynecologic Practice and Practice Committee. Female age-related fertility decline: committee opinion No. 589. *Fertil Steril*. 2014;101(3):633–634. doi: 10.1016/j.fertnstert.2013.12.032
13. [Juan Balasch](#)¹, [Eduard Gratacós](#). Delayed childbearing: effects on fertility and the outcome of pregnancy. *Curr Opin Obstet Gynecol*. 24(3):187-93. 2012 Jun; doi: 10.1097/GCO.0b013e3283517908
14. Hamilton JA 1, Cissen M 2, Brandes M 3 et.al. Total motile sperm count: a better indicator for the severity of male factor infertility than the WHO sperm classification system. *Human Reproduction* (Oxford, England), 18 Mar 2015, 30(5):1110-1121. <https://doi.org/10.1093/humrep/dev058>
15. [FAM Kersten](#)¹, [R P G M Hermens](#)², [D D M Braa](#) et.al. Overtreatment in couples with unexplained infertility. *Hum Reprod*. 2015 Jan;30(1):71-80. doi: 10.1093/humrep/deu262. Epub 2014 Oct 21
16. ESHRE Capri Workshop Group . A prognosis-based approach to infertility: understanding the role of time. *Human Reproduction*, Volume 32, Issue 8, August 2017, Pages 1556–1559, <https://doi.org/10.1093/humrep/dex214>

17. Athanasios Chalazonitis, Ioanna Tzovara, Fotios Laspas et.al. Hysterosalpingography: technique and applications. *Curr Probl Diagn Radiol*. 2009 Sep-Oct;38(5):199-205. doi: 10.1067/j.cpradiol.2008.02.003.
18. [R Rajah¹](#), [J M McHugo](#), [M Obhrai](#). The role of hysterosalpingography in modern gynaecological practice. *Br J Radiol*. 1992 Oct;65(778):849-51. doi: 10.1259/0007-1285-65-778-849.
19. Maheux-Lacroix S, Boutin A, Moore L, Bergeron ME et.al. [Hysterosalpingosonography for diagnosing tubal occlusion in subfertile women: a systematic review with meta-analysis](#). *Hum Reprod*. 2014 May; 29(5): 953-63. doi: 10.1093/humrep/deu024.
20. [William L Simpson Jr¹](#), [Laura G Beitia](#), [Jolinda Mester](#). Hysterosalpingography: a reemerging study. *Radiographics*. 2006 Mar-Apr;26(2):419-31. doi: 10.1148/rg.262055109.

